

The Influence of Russia's Feminist Antiwar Resistance to Putin's Impact on the War in Ukraine

Frederick M. Burkle, Jr., MD, MPH, DTM, PhD (Hon.), FACEP, FAAP

Global Scholar

Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars

Washington, DC

Captain (MC) USNR (Ret)

Institute of Medicine, National Academy of Medicine: Elected '07

Tel: (808) 262-2098

Email: Skipmd77@aol.com

Amir Khorram-Manesh, MD, PhD

Department of Surgery, Institute of Clinical Sciences.

Gothenburg Emergency Medicine Research Group

Sahlgrenska Academy, Gothenburg University

41345 Gothenburg, Sweden

Email: amir.khorram-manesh@surgery.gu.se

Author Note

This article is based on the authors' research about abusive antisocial personality, especially in current dictators. Both authors have experience in both psychiatry and war. The first author is, among others, a specialist in psychiatry.

Abstract

Sociopathic leadership may not only result in domestic oppression but also in international conflicts, affecting civilian lives internally and globally. In this article, the authors inform the consequences of such Russian-led leadership in previous wars and conflicts to those involved in the current war in Ukraine focusing on the unique and persistent Russian female civilian-led organized opposition to the war.

Keywords: Ukraine, anti-war, conflict, narcissism, resistance, war

Introduction

Since February 2022, the Russian invasion of Ukraine has resulted in over 23,000 civilian, 120,000 Ukrainian military, and 200,000 Russian military casualties (Remondelli et al., 2023). Additionally, hundreds of thousands have left Russia. Although most Russians may report that little has changed in the tenor of the country despite the imposed international sanctions, sanctions have affected prices and left people with no freedom of speech or information-sharing with nothing but silence, making it impossible to tell if people are being honest. Many Russians chose to stay away from politics and let the Kremlin decide for them, further acknowledging

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that “most ordinary Russians are in the middle, trying to make sense of a situation they didn’t choose, don’t understand, and feel powerless to change” (Goryanov, 2023).

However, in February 2020, the beginning of the war, after President Vladimir Putin announced a “special operation” against the neighboring sovereign state of Ukraine, the Feminist Anti-war Resistance (FAR) launched the first and one of the largest pacifist movements through a manifesto that reads: “Russian citizens and feminists, we condemn this war. Feminism as a political force cannot be on the side of the war of aggression and military occupation.” (Koltsova, 2022; Europe Solidaire Sans Frontieres, 2022). The FAR authors emphasize that the Russian history of cult-like support and admiration of their leaders has resulted in a current “ruthless hyper-masculine image” of which Putin is now seen as the “epitome.” The FAR coordinator’s response was to endorse that “war crimes are occurring in Ukraine, domestic abuse has been decriminalized, and policemen have a license to torture and beat their fellow citizens.” Citizens can even be imprisoned just for discussing the war (Koltsova, 2022; Kirby, 2022).

A few may know that there is a long tradition, dating from World War I, of female activists and others in opposition to war in Russia. An opposition that was shared with many other countries, resulting in the Hague Women’s Peace Conference with worldwide attendance. Similar feminist groups sprang up across nations to demonstrate against nuclear weapons. Fewer in Western countries are aware of the history of the Committee of Soldiers’ Mothers of Russia (CSMR) and their efforts, through activism, to mitigate and trace the mother’s organized response to both the loss of their sons as well as the purposeful violence they endured and were subject to (Elkner, 2004). It was especially evident in the reign of Gorbachev, beginning in 1985 when the CSMR helped expose to the public the “widespread systems of informed power hierarchies that operated in Soviet barracks and the associated violence in which senior conscripts bullied and victimized recruits.” (Elkner, 2004). Over the decades significant resistance has grown against Russian militarism catalyzed by a feminist dissident group in 1980 that has since demonstrated first condemning the war in Afghanistan in 1980 and again as a “Feminism led political force” demanding military reform and resistance to the First Chechen War in the 1990s (Talaver, 2023).

In responding to the war in Chechnya, CSMR, which had experience in rehabilitation, responded to the soldiers leaving for health reasons. As in the past, the mothers-led organization “expanded and diversified to include human rights education, especially human rights violations, including non-violent public protests and prevention of anti-democratic changes in the Russian military legislation that fought against involuntary conscription (Right Livelihood, 2023). The formation of such a powerful group of mothers and women originates from the Russian long history of developing permanent female gender roles that are anti-masculinity in both war and household responsibilities, clarifying Russia’s history of “cult-like support for the military and admiration of leaders who project a ruthless hyper-masculine image.” Meanwhile, Russia has also a history of high domestic violence problems with little support for women trying to flee these relationships (Europe Solidaire Sans Frontieres, 2023). These factors together with both psychological and physical impacts have been highlighted in Russian society,

resulting in strong female organizations, e.g., CSMR with strong opposition to war and violence (Stewart & Robinson, 1998).

Addressing the Current War in Ukraine

Fast forward to the war in Ukraine. Thousands of Russian soldiers have been conscripted and over 300,000 reservists were called up to fight the declared “special operation,” denying it a war status. This prompted a meeting between President Putin and the powerful CSMR on Mother’s Day November 27, 2022. While Putin organized the meeting to be surrounded by supporters, he was faced with accusations by FAR of seeding the audience with those strongly faithful to the war. In a video later circulated widely, the FAR President asked Putin “Do you have the courage to look us in the eye, not with hand-picked women and mothers in your pocket, but with real women, who have traveled from various cities here to meet with you?” The FAR women publicly sought to “quell fears about the poor treatment, inadequate training, and other dangers faced by Russian Troops.” Criticisms ran high. Veteran soldiers’ rights activists had previously reported that they expected that the Kremlin would handpick--or even fake--its roster of soldiers’ mothers for the event to prevent a scandal from unfolding. In this meeting, all responsible reports suggest that Putin simply chose women with proven pro-Kremlin bona fides who would not challenge the Russian president over the war (Roth & Sauer, 2023).

One cannot deny the power of the decisions made by “Mothers” and their often-visible citizen support. As retired veterans of war and conflict, we are not immune to the struggles these organizations must face to have their voices heard. Thus, being a voice for these women, we should tell the mothers, sisters, and wives of deployed Russian soldiers to Ukraine, “We sincerely feel your pain and anxiety. As professional experts on sociopathic leaders, we have witnessed global wars and conflicts led by so many autocrats since the end of World War II. Vladimir Putin is one of those despots, currently probably the most terrifying dictator in the world (Burkle, 2016). You deserve to know how and why Putin is driven to rule, how far he will go to maintain power, and how he longs to take control of other nations. All sons, husbands, and brothers are among many who will be victimized to satisfy Putin’s obsessions. While he claims to be a savior or patriot, his final psychological framework differs little from those tyrants responsible for World War II and the Cold War that followed (Khorram-Manesh & Burkle, 2022).

Putin’s Impact

Readers should better understand why sociopathic leaders exist and, importantly, why they are incapable of change or mediation, factors inherent in a narcissistic sociopath’s behavior. Unfortunately, a certain percentage of the global population can be identified with unique, often troublesome, and yet poorly understood personality characteristics early on in their lives. During normal childhood, children learn to experience personal anxiety, doubt, shame, depression, guilt, etc., and establish both age-appropriate neurologically and socially beneficial developmental tasks, resulting in a healthy curiosity, critical reflection, perception, sound judgment, and foundations of ethics, morality, and empathy. However, the absence of such development results in narcissism, deteriorated ego, and immaturity in a certain portion of the

young population. You may only know of their presence as a subset of the population who are driven to seek the ultimate opportunity to control, dictate, and live out their fantasies of power on the world stage. Their attempt to control others, whether they be individuals or countries who challenge them, most always culminates in violence. The dictator's continued antisocial presence, influence, and the levels of violence they unleash must be seen as a global security issue. Unfortunately, this issue is not amenable to any conventional diplomatic intervention, negotiation, or international sanctions. All of you have witnessed this fact for months, if not the entire two decades of President Putin's rule (Burkle, 2016; Khorram-Manesh & Burkle, 2022).

You should know that the traits displayed by such individuals are not that of a mental illness but of discernible character disorders beginning at a young age with socially undesirable behavior, poor control of impulses, and an inability to maintain emotional relationships, especially in marriage. Such individuals also display the absence of anxiety or guilt. Prominent is an inflated sense of self-importance, a need for constant attention, an expectation of special treatment, exaggerating achievements, being intolerant of criticism, and obsession with power (Burkle, 2015). This "narcissism" is further distinguished by excessive admiration for oneself, selfishness, a sense of entitlement, lack of empathy for others, need for constant admiration, and self-centeredness that fails to distinguish or consider the needs of others.

You should know that the discernible character disorder you have witnessed with Putin is not a mental illness. His narcissism drives him to think only of himself. The protracted conflict in Ukraine ensures a political impasse that results in ever more persecution, violence, destruction, fleeing refugee populations, and death (Khorram-Manesh & Burkle, 2022; Khorram-Manesh & Burkle, 2023). Putin's narcissistic sociopathy is playing out on the world stage for everyone to ponder. Strong sociopaths such as Putin can transfer their "logic" onto an unaware population. It is the reason he met with you publicly to make his case: You are sacrificing your loved ones for him, not for Russia. We are all easily impressed and fooled by a narcissist's impassioned dictates, and either we collectively feel powerless to do anything to prevent his obsessions, or we are frightened by the consequences of challenging the leader's constant demand for power.

Only the masses of his victims and potential targets hold the key to demanding a collective cessation of his malignant behavior. The Soldier's Mothers of Russia is a critical start, and the base of resistance remains. One recent report reveals that some of these unexpected protestors were once Putin supporters; others still believe the war in Ukraine is a just one and want their men to come home (Sauer, 2024). Although severely stifled it speaks for the mothers, sisters, and wives of soldiers in the war in Ukraine.

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